

Kinetics of Decarboxylation of Malonic Acid in Some Solvents*

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Malonic acid and substituted malonic acids are known to undergo decarboxylation in alkanols, amines and diols and the rate has been observed by various workers to follow a first order kinetics. We have measured the rate of decarboxylation of malonic acid in several solvents, ethylene glycol, 1:2 propane diol, 1:3 butane diol, diethylene-, polyethylene-, and polypropylene glycols. It is seen that the first order rate equation fits the decarboxylation data in all these solvents. The values of the rate constants are lowered in diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols. The entropy of activation suggests that the transition state complex in these solvents is probably having a less rigid structure.

DECARBOXYLATION of malonic acid has been the subject of many investigations¹ in presence of quinoline and related solvents. The Fraenkel mechanism² suggests formation of an activated complex formed due to the attraction between electrophilic carbonyl carbon and the lone pair of electrons on the nucleophilic N-atom of the quinoline nucleus. It has been observed that unsymmetrical disubstituted malonic acid produces a racemic mixture and not optically active disubstituted acetic acid^{3,4}. This implies carbon-carbon double bond formation at some point in the reaction course. This produces a good evidence in support of the Fraenkel mechanism. Further the rate determining step in the decarboxylation of malonic acid is likely to be the breaking of C—C bond rather than the formation or dissociation of the hydrogen bond⁴.

In the present investigation we have undertaken the studies of the decarboxylation kinetics of malonic acid in ethylene glycol, propane-1, 2-diol, 1,3-butanediol, diethylene glycol (DEG), polyethylene glycol-400 (PEG) and polypropylene glycol-425 (PPG). Such studies are likely to provide a comparison of the decarboxylation kinetics in diols vis a vis diethylene- and other polymeric glycols. It may be mentioned that some of the decarboxylation kinetics in diols have been studied by other workers previously¹. Our results compare favourably with literature.

Experimental

Materials: Malonic acid, white crystalline solid (Reidel, Germany) was used without further purification.

Ethylene glycol, (Pfizer, India) was used after distilling twice under reduced pressure. The solvents

polyethylene glycol-400 (B.D.H., England), 1, 3-butanediol, (Fluka, Switzerland), propane-1, 2-diol (B.D.H. Lab. reagent), diethylene glycol (B.D.H., England) and polypropylene glycol-425 (Koch-Light, England) were used without further purification.

Rates were determined by collecting CO₂ gas in a gas burette at various intervals of time over an aqueous solution⁵ prepared by mixing 20% by weight of sodium sulphate and 5% by volume of sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) coloured with methyl red. Temperature was controlled in a thermostat within $\pm 0.2^\circ$. Heavy grade liquid paraffin was used as the bath liquid. The reaction flask was attached by a light stand to a vibrating plate, resulting in constant and rapid stirring of the reaction mixture.

The gas burette was surrounded by a wider Jacket through which water at room temperature was circulated. In each run the amount of malonic acid was about 0.167 gm in 25 cc of the solvent, previously saturated with dry carbon dioxide gas. Stoichiometry was checked in all the solvents by collecting carbon dioxide gas after the reaction was complete.

Results and Discussion

It has been previously established that malonic acid and substituted malonic acids undergo a first order decarboxylation kinetics in alkanols, diols and phenols^{1,5,6}. In Table 1 are given the first order rate constants in ethylene glycol, propane-1, 2-diol, 1, 3-butanediol, diethylene glycol, polyethylene glycol and polypropylene glycol at several temperatures between 120°-160°. The rate constants were determined from the slope of the linear plot of log

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$\frac{V_{\infty}}{V_{\infty} - V_t}$ against t , time; V_t is the volume of carbon dioxide produced at time, t and V_{∞} represents the final volume of carbon dioxide produced in an experiment. Decarboxylation kinetics was studied over a wide concentration range in ethylene glycol solvent between 0.089–0.668 gm of malonic acid in 25 ml of the solvent in each set of experiment. The rate constants at various concentrations of malonic acid are given in Table 3.

It has been noted that malonic acid decarboxylates rather slowly in the solvents, diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols at temperature below 140°. In diols, on the other hand, the decarboxylation rate is appreciable at 120° as will be evident from Table 1. In fact, the rate constant is decreased about three fold in the solvents DEG, PEG, and PPG relative to the values in diols.

We have evaluated enthalpy of activation, $\Delta H^\ddagger$,

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID

Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Rate constants $\times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$					
		120	130	140	145	150	160
1. Ethylene glycol		5.3	11.9	21.6	30.3	—	—
2. 1,2-Propane diol		5.5	9.5	20.0	25.5	—	—
3. 1,3-Butane diol		7.8	15.8	24.5	26.6	—	—
4. Polyethylene glycol (400)		—	—	6.2	7.6	14.7	16.5
5. Diethylene glycol		—	—	9.6	14.0	—	—
6. Polypropylene glycol (425)		3.5	4.5	9.9	12.7	14.4	—

It is seen that decarboxylation follows a first order rate over this concentration range at 140°. And evidently the same reaction mechanism operates in low and high concentrations of malonic acid. It is interesting to note that first order rate law is observed in the molten state of malonic acid. Our data compare favourably with those of Clark¹. These are shown in Table 2.

and entropy of activation, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for the decarboxylation process by applying the absolute reaction rate theory,

$$k_t = \frac{kT}{h} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{RT}\right) \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R) \quad \dots (1)$$

to the rate constant data in a solvent at several temperatures as given in Table 1. In equation (1) k_t

TABLE 2—DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS : THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Solvents	^a Enthalpy of activation $\Delta H^\ddagger$ (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	^b Entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)	Free energy $\Delta F^\ddagger_{140^\circ}$ (Kcal mole ⁻¹)
1. Ethylene glycol	19.9	-23.2	29.3
2. 1,2-Propane diol	19.5	-24.4	29.4
3. 1,3-Butane diol	15.8	-32.7	29.2
4. Polyethylene glycol	25.8	-11.6	30.5
5. Diethylene glycol	24.7	-13.2	30.1
6. Polypropylene glycol	21.9	-20.08	30.1
7. Malonic acid (molten)	32.7	8.5	29.2
	35.8 ^c	11.9 ^c	
	33.0 ^d	4.5 ^d	

a, b : $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are the average values over the temperature range studied.

c : reference 7 ; d : reference 8.

TABLE 3—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID IN ETHYLENE GLYCOL AT 140° AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Weight of Malonic acid in 25 ml Ethylene glycol (gm)	Rate constant $\times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.089	23.0
0.1670	21.5
0.2773	21.1
0.6686	17.5

is the rate constant at the temperature $T^{\circ}\text{K}$; k , R and h are Boltzmann constant, molar gas constant and Planck's constant respectively. With $\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$ thus known, it is easy to calculate the free energy of activation, $\Delta F^{\ddagger}_{135^{\circ}}$, at a temperature $t = 135^{\circ}$ from the relation

$$\Delta F^{\ddagger} = \Delta H^{\ddagger} - T\Delta S^{\ddagger}$$

In Table 2 are compared the thermodynamic parameters, $\Delta H^{\ddagger}$, $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta F^{\ddagger}_{135^{\circ}}$ for the decarboxylation process in these solvents. It is seen that the values of $\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ are much higher in diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols. The values of $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$, on the other hand, are less negative in diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols, which implies a relatively loose transition state complex in such solvents. It would appear that the energy factor is mainly responsible for lowering the rate constant in these solvents. In Table 2 we have included the values of $\Delta F^{\ddagger}_{135^{\circ}}$ for decarboxylation of malonic acid at its melting point, 135° , in the molten state and in the various solvents, and the values of $\Delta F^{\ddagger}_{135^{\circ}}$ are almost constant for the diols and molten malonic acid. This implies that the rate constants in the diols as evaluated using equation (i) are the same as that for molten malonic acid at its melting point. This finding is in agreement with that of Clark¹ who established the existence of isokinetic temperature for a series of solvents. However, the values of $\Delta F^{\ddagger}_{135^{\circ}}$ at 135° in the remaining solvents, diethylene-, polyethylene-, and polypropylene glycols are 30.1, 30.5 and 30.1 Kcal/mole respectively which are considerably larger than the value of $\Delta F^{\ddagger}_{135^{\circ}}$ at 135° for pure malonic acid. Thus while it is possible to obtain correct rate constant for malonic acid by substituting the values of $\Delta F^{\ddagger}_{135^{\circ}}$ at 135° obtained for diols in equation (1), it is seen that the decarboxylation rate for pure molten malonic acid cannot be correlated with the rates in the solvents diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols. Moreover an inspection of the rate constants and thermodynamic parameters

(Tables 1 and 2) shows clearly that DEG, PEG and PPG constitute a group of solvents playing a similar role with respect to decarboxylation reaction and differing from alkane diols.

It is remarkable to note that the rate constants and the thermodynamic parameters $\Delta F^{\ddagger}$, $\Delta S^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ in DEG are very close to those in PEG and PPG. Evidently the presence of ether linkage and not its number is responsible for decreased rates of decarboxylation in these solvents compared to that in alkane diols.

The entropy of activation for decarboxylation of malonic acid in DEG, PEG and PPG are less negative than what is observed in diols (Table 2). This suggests that the transition state complex in these solvents, namely diethylene-, polyethylene-, and polypropylene glycols are probably having a less rigid structure.

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